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CONSOLIDATION IN THE FINANCIAL SECTOR: CHALLENGES AND PROSPECTS OF BUREAU DE CHANGE

BY

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INTRODUCTION

The Nigerian Financial Services Industry comprises banking, capital markets, insurance, asset management, pensions and other financial institutions. As at December 2006, there were 1,805 banks and other financial institutions in the financial sector.

Reforms in the Nigerian economy started in 1986, with the partial deregulation of the foreign exchange market (through the creation of the second tier foreign exchange market, SFEM) and the privatization program.

By 2003, the Government embarked on more fundamental reforms aimed at reinvigorating the economy, reducing poverty,. Creating jobs, improving public infrastructure, entrenching fiscal discipline in public budgeting and expenditure, restructuring the public service for greater efficiency and effectiveness and enabling the private sector to achieve greater performance and growth.

This paper examines the rationale options and process of consolidation in the financial sector, the structure and operational modalities of the foreign exchange market in Nigeria and the impact of consolidation on the bureaux de change.

Bank Consolidation in Nigeria

The Nigeria banking sector has undergone remarkable changes over the years, in terms of the number of institutions, ownership structure as well as the depth and breadth of operations. These changes have been influenced largely by the challenges posed by the deregulation of the sector, globalization of operations, technological innovations, and the adoption of supervisory and prudential requirements that conform to international standards. The deregulation of the sector, which began during the period of 1986 to 1990, was followed by a flood of new banks. The existence of so many banks coupled with the non-compliance with market regulations by majority of the players, poor management, poor credit policy insider dealings/abuses, economic recession etc. to distress in the banking industry in the 1990s.

Furthermore, CBN's surveillance on banks recently revealed deterioration in banks overall performance, based on CAMEL parameters. Banks' performance rating in 2004 showed that 10 banks were rated as sound, while 51,16 and 10 banks were rated as satisfactory, marginal and unsound, respectively. Against this background, the CBN in July 2004 rolled out a 13-point reform agenda aimed at consolidating the banking sector and preventing the occurrence of systemic distress.

Two major elements in the reform package were the requirement that the minimum capitalization for banks should be N25 billion with effect from ending of December 2005 and that the consolidation of banking institutions through mergers and acquisitions should be initiated.

Some of the goals the CB intends to achieve by consolidating the Nigerian banking sector include:

- Creating a sound and more secure banking system that depositors can trust.
- Building domestic banks that investors can rely upon to finance investment in the Nigerian economy.
- Encouraging industry consolidation and reducing systemic risks.
- Righting corruption and white-collar crimes through improved transparency and accountability and insisting on sound corporate governance practices in the finances services.
- Driving down cost structure of banks, improving banks' efficiency and encouraging competition with goals of lowering interest rates and providing cheap credit to the economy and
- Meeting international benchmarks and minimum requirements for the integration of regional financial systems.

RATIONALE FOR CONSOLIDATION IN THE FINANCIAL SECTOR

Business consolidation through mergers and acquisition has become a global phenomenon to achieve economies of scale and higher productivity. The need for financial institutions to merge becomes even more imperative in the face of the onslaught of greater competition arising from globalization and the pressure under World Trade Organization (WTO) for countries to open up their financial markets to further entry of foreign banks. For this reason, many countries are moving towards consolidating their banking system and Nigeria cannot be an exception.

A number of reasons have been advanced on why firms are consolidating or merging and some importance factors driving consolidation have been identified. Our focus is on bank consolidation, but one should note that much of the same philosophy and rationale for bank mergers applies to other industries as well. Two primary factors affecting the need for banks to remain competitive are technology and deregulation.

Whilst, technology has blurred the lines of specialization among financial intermediaries, deregulation has significantly changed the way banks do business and where they do business.

Technological improvement also means more change and the breakdown of traditional barriers, such as geography and product varieties. The two forces of technology and deregulation, working together, have resulted in what is referred to as the global economy. Also, the mixing together of technology and deregulation has produced rapid change that increasingly blurs accepted boundaries of time, geography, language, industries, enterprises, economies and regulations. As a result, many merger partners today are creating financial supermarkets, where customers can have one-stop financial services.

In addition to market consolidations, regulatory factors have accounted for some bank consolidation in different parts of the world. For example, the consolidation that took place in Lebanon, Malaysia, Kenya and South Africa were mainly policy-induced.

The justification for consolidation and enhanced capital requirement for Nigeria banks lies in the weakness condition of the banking sector. In addition, there were a large number of small players that could not operate profitably in a narrow margin market.

Several of them were unable to support the real sector of the economy because of their small practices in order to make ends meet.

Finally, several of the banks operated a weak corporate governance structure, reflecting rudimentary, internal controlled banks. Thus, the banking sector reforms initiated by the CBN were designed to ensure a diversified, strong and reliable banking sector that will ensure the safety of depositors' money, as well as enable the banks play active developmental role in the Nigeria economy, and have the capability of emerging as competent and competitive players in the regional and global financial system. The reforms were aimed at creating a strong banking system, while consolidation was expected to address the problems of distress and technically insolvent institution without resorting to the liquidation option.

LESSONS FROM OTHER COUNTRIES

The financial services industry is restructuring and consolidating at an unprecedented pace around the globe. Particularly, in the United State and Western Europe transactions are numerous and breathtaking. Restructuring is also going on Asia. Most striking is probably the ever-escalating scale of mergers in banking. In the US, there has been over 7,000 cases of bank mergers since 1980, while the same trend occurred in the UK and other Europe countries. Specifically, in the period 1997, 1998, 203 bank merger and acquisitions took place in the Euro area. In 1998 a merger in France resulted in a new bank with a capital base of US \$688 billion, while the merger of two banks in Germany in the same year created the second largest bank in Germany with a capital base of Us \$541 billion. In many emerging markets, including Argentina, Brazil and Korea, consolidation has also become prominent as banks strive to become more competitive and resilient to shocks as well as reposition their operations to cope with the challenges of the increasingly globalized banking systems.

Other benefits derivable from consolidation in the financial sector include:

- Greater efficiency and cost effectiveness;
- Enhanced ability to compete in the market place, both domestically and internationally;
- Leveraging on technology; and
- Diversification of operations, controlling risks and provisions of broader array of products.

THE ECONOMIC EFFECTS OF BUREAU DE CHANGE IN NIGERIA

Two prices are very crucial in any economy, they are: the interest rate and the exchange rate. Achievement of both internal and external balance demand that the two rates must be realistic in the light of the economic position of a nation. It was in a bid to achieve this among other objectives that some firms were licenced in 1989 to start buying and selling of foreign currencies. These firms were tagged "**Bureau-De-Change**".

THE EXCHANGE RATE

The exchange rate simply defined is the price at which one currency is exchange or another currency. The actual rate any one time is determined in the foreign exchange market. The foreign exchange market is an organizational framework within which firms, individuals and banks can buy and sell currencies. It is important to note that transaction may be on spot market or forward market. The spot exchange market is the market for buying and selling of currencies for immediate delivery, say two days while the forward exchange market is the market for buying and selling of currencies for future delivery, usually 90 days.

In a free market, the actual rate at any one time is determined by the supply and demand conditions for the relevant currencies in the market. These as we know would depend on the Balance of Payments deficits or surpluses of the relevant economies and the demand for the currencies to meet obligations and expectations about the future movements in the rate. One important fact we should note here is that the demand for foreign currency, say the Dollar by Nigerian ultimately means the supply of the Nigerian Naira and demand for this naira by the United States in exchange for the Dollar.

BUREAU DE CHANGE IN NIGERIA: GENESIS OF EXISTENCE

Apart from the above irregularities, it was found out that small buyers and sellers of foreign currencies were not receiving attention in most of these banks. The resultant effect of this is that most of these small buyers and sellers end up patronizing the 'parallel' market with its attending risks. Again, most of these dealings will normally go unaccounted for. It was in a bid to remove these irregularities that the idea of licensing some firms to buy and sell foreign currencies came into being as announced in the President Budget Speech of 1989.

Specifically, the Bureau-de-change was established with the following four basic objectives:

- To accord legal recognition to small dealers in foreign exchange and thereby enhance the size of the officially recognized foreign market;
- To provide free access to foreign exchange by small buyers in a convenient and informal manner thereby filling gaps in service under the existing arrangements;
- To enhance efficiency in macro-economic management through more adequate statistical coverage of foreign exchange flows;
- To improve fiscal efficiency.

The following are some of the operational guidelines of the Bureau-de-change:

- Ideally, they are expected to deal only in the bank notes and coins and the purchase of travelers cheques.
- The foreign currencies dealt in by the Bureau-de-change shall be derived only from private sources.
- Sellers shall not be required and if required shall not be obliged to disclose the source.
- Transaction shall be on cash and carry basis.
- Buying and selling rates shall be subject to a maximum spread of 23.
- Maximum commission chargeable for bank notes and travelers cheques shall be one quarter of one percent.

There are other operational guidelines as contained in the Bureau-de-change guidelines issued by the Central Bank of Nigeria.

The Bureau-de-change were specifically barred from sourcing their foreign exchange from banks operating in Nigeria including the Central Bank of Nigeria (CBN). The (CBN) shall supervise and monitor the operations of Bureau-de-change to ensure orderly conduct and development of this segment of the foreign exchange market. They are expected to render monthly returns to the CBN. This is to enable the CBN have accurate data of the inflow and outflow of foreign exchange through this segment of the foreign exchange market.

As contained in the a989 Budgets, they are supposed to be medium-sized private sector firm that will be licensed with the sole purpose of buying and selling foreign currencies from and to private sources. They are expected to be more flexible than the more bureaucracy-dominated official foreign exchange market. Also, they are to be less restrictive, and they are, checks for the unofficial parallel market. The hope was that the FOREX Bureau would succeed where the autonomous market failed.

BUREAU-DE-CHANGE IN NIGERIA: HOW FAR?

Bureau-de-change are companies that carry out foreign exchange business on a stand-alone basis, in accordance with Foreign Exchange (Monitoring & Miscellaneous Provisions) Act of 1995. There are about 126 licensed bureau de change in Nigeria.

In this section, we present result of our findings on the economic effects of the operation of FOREX Bureau on the Nigerian economy. It is customary in economics to find out the benefits and costs accruing from and to a particular scheme either in ex ante or ex post form. Here, we have done the two, that is, we present the economic effects that have been observed and those that we expect. As a good starting point however, we hereby review the results of Ghana's experience from the operation of Bureau-de-change. This is normal for several reasons:

Both economics are results of colonialism

They both share similar economic problems

In operating the new foreign exchange arrangement, three markets have emerged in both countries, viz: the official exchange market, the official parallel market and the illegal market.

Lastly, the scheme started in Ghana as far back as March, 1988.

A. REVIEW OF BUREAU-DE-CHANGE IN GHANA

Licensed to operate since March, 1988, two categories of bureau were established individual and bank-owned. As at the end of 1988, 85 of the bureau in operation were located in the greater Accra Region.

According to experts, the scheme has been in success in Ghana in that Ghanaians public responded enthusiastically to the scheme. Many of them no longer go to official auction system for foreign currencies and the bureau have provided some measure of succor to small and medium sized operators in Ghana. It was also reported that, many Ghanaians even responded by sending money to their relations through the bureau system. On the average, each bureau handles a turnover of C3 million on a daily basis.

With the introduction of the scheme however, no significant appreciation of Cedi been recorded. In fact, there has been depreciation. The Cedi witnessed 35% depreciation from C260 at inception of the FOREX bureau to C360 for a US\$ as at January, 1989 investigation revealed that the value of Cedi could have been depreciated much more but for the easy and uncomplicated access to the market, coupled with the relative large number of dealing houses.

One important impact the existence of bureau de change have led in Ghana was the reduction in the dealers in the black market patronage. According to reports, most of the dealers in the black market have more or less been reduced to mere middlemen between the forex bureau and the customers. However, operators of forex bureau still have to contend with competition from the black market. Their operations have only reduced the size of the black market, a significant number of operators of black market still exist.

B. THE ECONOMIC EFFECTS OF FOREX IN NIGERIA

In analyzing the economic effects of forex in Nigeria, special attention will have to be paid to the basic objectives, which their establishment is supposed to achieve. We shall also consider other associated economic effect that we will observed.

(a). bureau and the Public

Two of the four stated objectives of forex Bureau are: to accord legal recognition to small dealers and to provide free access to foreign exchange by small buyers in a convenient and informal manner thereby filling the gaps in service under the then existing arrangements. This has been achieved to a greater extent. Immediately after the announcement, people started besieging the Central Bank Office to find out the necessary requirements. By September 12, 1989, sixty firms have been licensed to operate bureau-de-change this is significant number considering the time period of first batch of six were licenced.

Reports have also indicated that except for the first few days of operation during which enquiries were being made, business transactions are bubbling as buyers and sellers run-into themselves in most of the offices of these bureau. Many come to buy to meet urgent domestic commitments while others come to buy foreign currencies for importation or mainly motor spare parts and second-hand vehicles. These are been a disproportionate demand for foreign currencies from these bureau. Every indication shows that a transaction at this bureau is increasing day in, day out.

The above has a lot of implications economically. First, owners of Bureau-De-Change will pay tax to the government; they have now received official recognition and thus can now deal in foreign exchange. Since their transactions are record, this has enhanced data collection on foreign currencies demand and supply. This will lead to a more accurate planning and forecasting by monetary authority on foreign exchange requirements which has hitherto been done on guess work. Secondly the establishment of the forex bureau gave opportunities to several Nigerians who will not have got access to the market. Small holders now have free access to the exchange market both for buying and selling. Since bureau operate on cash and carry basis, much time is not wasted and administrative delays is reduced. This saves a since 'time is money' in business. Again, since most buyers use the foreign currencies to import goods, such goods will not the available in the market, the import duties that will be paid on these goods will enhance the revenue accruing to the government.

It is important to not one scenario that has developed in recent times among the Nigerian public. The rush among Nigerians nowadays has been to 'check' out of the country, to go and work and bring back their earned income. The easy access to the foreign market has encouraged this. Apart from improving the standard of living of such people when they come back, there can be a resultant increase in the supply of foreign currencies. Furthermore, this scenario has reduced considerably the number of people living in the country, most especially youths.

The activities of the bureau have saved a lot people from the risk associated with the market and that of being charged for illegal dealings.

(b). Bureau and the Black Market

Another major aim of establishing the forex bureau was to eliminate the 'black market'.

With increasing tempo of activities at most of these bureau at inception, it was thought that sooner or later, the parallel market will crumble as the Exchange Bureau further consolidate their grip on the market and as more operators get their licenses. However, months after this, observation have revealed that the black market has not crumbles.

What we have only seen is a reduction in the activities in the black market as experienced in Ghana. This is because most people have abandoned the black market.

According to an expert, this stems from the fact that people trust the forex bureau because they have an office. Again, the risk of being given fake notes is reduced.

Infact, operators of the black market have admitted that the market has slacked since the bureau were licenced.

One important point we can derive from the above analysis is that the activities in the black market has reduced at least to an extent. This will enhance accuracy of statistics on foreign currencies and thus facilitates economic planning. Revenue will also accrue to government from this claimed source.

(c).Bureau and Government Revenue

Revenue will accrue to government and its agencies through the activities of these forex bureau. First, Bureau-de-change according to the enabling regulations are to operate within the provisions of the companies Decree of 1968 and other statutory and regulatory provisions including those relating to prescribed return for Income Tax purposes. This means that, forex bureau will have to pay income tax to the government.

This will enhance government revenue. Second, people employed by these firms will have to pay monthly tax under the PAYE system. A conservative estimate of N3,600 has been projected for this per month. This gives a yearly return of about N43, 200.

Whatever may be the case, it is expected that there will be increase in government tax revenue both from the company's income tax and the income tax of their workers.

In addition to the above, the commission payable to the Central Bank from their deals will also add to the revenue of the Central Bank of Nigeria.

Economically, increase in revenue means increase in money available to the government to execute its activities. Money derived from this course can be used to establish industrial projects, creates more jobs and enhances welfare. Social amenities apart from acting as a catalyst for industrial development also enhances welfare. We should at this stage note the multiplier effect of government expenditure. Creation of one job leads to creation of several others through linkage and multiplier effects therefore, ceteris paribus, with increase in revenue accruing to the government, there is going to be positive impact on the economy.

(d).Bureau and Employment

As Companies, forex bureau employ quite a sizeable number of people, observers believed that on the average, a bureau-de-change will need at least ten employees. The establishment of forex bureau in Nigeria has created employment opportunities for different grades of unemployed Nigerians. Their impact is much more appreciated when we recall that employment of one hand in Nigeria salvages three others unemployed from dying of hunger. This stems from our traditional family system.

The creation of jobs by the forex bureau inherently creates jobs for other people. The cumulative effect of all these is the increase in number of employed people. This development has a lot of implications the higher the number of people engaged in productive ventures, the higher the national income. Tax paid by these employed people goes to government as additional revenue. The decrease in the number of unemployed reduces the dependency ratio, increases standard of living and reduces societal ills. The list is endless. One important act we should not is that the existence of the bureau-de-change has created employment opportunities with lots of attached positive effect on the economy.

(e). Bureau and the Exchange Rate

As stated earlier on, inherent in the objectives of deregulating the foreign exchange market is the achievement of a realistic exchange rate for naira. However, observation has revealed that the establishment of forex has not stemmed continuous depreciation of the naira. This was also experienced in Ghana. One common feature of the Interbank Foreign exchange Market (IFEM) which has spilled into the bureau operation is the disproportionate demand for foreign exchange relative to supply. The first fundamental problem faced by the first batch of the forex bureau was that of sourcing enough foreign exchange to run profitable bureau. Even, very optimistic operators have found that supply is short of demand.

Following out theory reviewed. The resultant effect of the above is depreciating naira. The economic effect of this has been with us since the introduction of the exchange market. The industrial sector has not gained much whereas the banking sector are swimming in huge and increasing profits. This shows that solution to the problem of a realistic exchange rate is yet to appear in sight.

DEVELOPMENT IMPLICATIONS OF CURRENT REFORMS ON FOREIGN EXCHANGE MARKET

Foreign exchange is the means of effecting payment for international transactions. It is made up of convertible currencies, interests bearing bonds, gold, Special Drawing rights (SDR) of the IMF, etc. that are generally accepted for the settlement of international trade and other external obligations. Among the key currencies are the United States Dollar, British Pound Sterling, European Euro, Japanese Yen, and the Canadian Dollar. A foreign exchange market is the medium of interaction between the sellers and buyers of foreign exchange in a bid to negotiate a mutually acceptable price for the settlement of international transactions. The foreign exchange market consists of the sellers (supply) and buyers (demand) of foreign exchange. The major participants in the foreign exchange market in Nigeria are the monetary authority (Central Bank of Nigeria) authorized dealers (banks), agents of the public sector, and the private sector as well as correspondent banks

abroad. Nigerians, resident abroad as well as invisible receipts derive the supply of foreign exchange from oil and non-oil exports, capital receipts including draw-sown on loans, expenditure of foreign tourists in Nigeria, repatriation of capital by the private sector and foreign grants. On the other hand, the demand for foreign exchange consists of payments for imports, external debt service obligations, personal home remittances (PHR) by foreign nationals resident in the country, financial commitments to international organizations and the country's embassies abroad, as well as other invisible out-payments by the public and private sectors.

EVOLUTION OF THE FOREIGN EXCHANGE MARKET

The evolution of the foreign exchange market in Nigeria up to its present state, had been influenced by a number of factors which include the changing pattern of international trade, institutional changes in the economy and structural shifts in production. Before the establishment of the Central Bank of Nigeria (CBN) in 1959 and the enactment of the Exchange Control Act of 1962, foreign exchange earned by the private sector was held in balances abroad by commercial banks which acted as agents for local exporters. During the period, agricultural exports contributed the bulk of foreign exchange earnings. The fact that the Nigerian Pound was tied to the British Pound Sterling at par, with easy convertibility, delayed the development of an active foreign exchange market. However, with the establishment of the CBN and the subsequent centralization of foreign exchange authority in the Bank, the need to develop a local foreign exchange market became imperative.

The increased export of crude oil in the early 1970s, following the sharp rise in its prices, enhanced official foreign exchange receipts. Thus, most economic agents had to patronize the CBN for foreign exchange allocation to pay for international transactions. However, as the oil market weakened and foreign reserves were depleted, comprehensive exchange control measures were introduced in 1982 to check the numerous activities of speculators and middlemen. The increasing demand for foreign exchange at the time supply was shrinking encouraged the development of a flourishing parallel market that emerged over time as a result of the inadequate supply of official foreign exchange led to various abuses including under-invoicing of exports and over-invoicing of imports. These resulted in capital flight and the diversion of official foreign exchange to the parallel market, a practice known as round tripping.

The exchange control measures turned out not to be an appropriate mechanism for foreign exchange allocation in consonance with the goal of internal balance. This led to introduction of the Second-tier Foreign Exchange Market (SFEM) in September 1986, whereby public sector transactions were carried out at official rate while all other transactions were conducted at market determined rates. To enlarge the scope of the foreign exchange market, bureau de change was introduced in 1989 to provide access to small user of foreign exchange.

In 1995, the foreign exchange market was further liberalized following the introduction of an Autonomous Foreign Exchange Market (AFEM) for the sale of foreign exchange to end users by the CBN through authorized dealers at market determined exchange rates. In 1999, the Inter-bank Foreign Exchange Market (IFEM) was introduced to deepen the foreign exchange market through the active participation of banks, oil companies, parastatals, non-banks financial institutions, bureau de change and private companies. The IFEM was abolished with the reintroduction of the subsidizing Dutch Auction System (DAS) in July 2002.

STRUCTURE OF NIGERIA'S FOREIGN EXCHANGE MARKET

Nigeria's foreign exchange market is made up of three major segments, the official, autonomous (made up of the inter-bank and bureau de change) and the parallel markets. The various segments of the market evolved over time owing to developments in the economy.

The operations of the official foreign exchange market, have metamorphosed over the years, particularly, since the introduction of exchange and trade liberalization policy in 1986. From the second-tier Foreign Exchange Market (SFEM) in September 1986, the official market was unified in 1987 when the exchange rate for public sector transactions was aligned with the commercial exchange rate.

The inter-bank market for free funds or privately sources foreign exchange was at the early stage dormant as foreign exchange was centralized in the CBN under the

1962 Exchange control Act. However, the market became vibrant with the introduction of SFEM and the permission granted banks by the CBN to effect foreign exchange dealings among themselves. The sharp practices which emanated from the system, in the form of round-tripping of funds, led to the persistent instability in the exchange rate.

Consequently, the official Foreign Exchange market and the Inter-bank Market were merged in 1989 into an enlarged Interbank Foreign Exchange market (IFEM). The bureau de change were established with the abolition of the inter-bank market in 1989 to accord access to small users of foreign exchange and enlarge the officially recognized foreign exchange market. Exchange rates in the bureau de change were market determined. In 1995, the official market evolved from a single to a dual exchange rate system in which a fixed exchange rate was applied for priority public sector transactions, while a market-based exchange rate was used for private sector transactions through the Autonomous foreign Exchange Market segment.

With the introduction of the AFEM in 1995, the banks were once more allowed to engage in interbank dealings with only privately sourced foreign exchange. However, the operations of the AFEM failed to meet the objectives for which it was set up. For instance, the inter-bank market, which was supposed to source its funds privately, relies on the CBN. In effect, the CBN continued to fund the various foreign exchange markets. The continued demand pressure arising from this arrangement which led to the depreciation of the naira at the foreign exchange markets, necessitated the introduction of some reforms in the foreign exchange market. By January 1999, the fixed official rate for priority public sector transactions was abolished, and all public sector transactions were conducted at the AFEM market-based rate. Indeed, the fixed official rate encouraged the existence of a large premium, which deepened the practice of round tripping, thus funding the bureau de change and parallel market. The elimination of the dual exchange rate system was followed by the introduction of another major reform, designed to check speculative tendencies that had been destabilizing the naira exchange rate and the consequent depreciation of the naira. On October 25, 1999, the AFEM was therefore replaced with the Inter-bank foreign Exchange market (IFEM). IFEM was conceived to deepen the foreign.

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